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Impact Factor: 0.98

RURAL BUSINESS STRATEGIC MODEL FOR RURAL MARKETS IN UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

India, being an agrarian economy, where agriculture sector makes its significant contribution of about 18% to the national Gross Domestic Product, has been divided into two: Urban India and Rural India. The gap between the two is getting widened due to high concentration of services' sector in Urban India. The urban India has resultantly raised its living standard in the presence of various urban facilities, which are not easily available to and accessible by the rural counter part of the country. No organized efforts have been made by the services' companies in supplying the various services like - medical facilities, vaccination, fast foods, matrimonial services, retailing, e-commerce, telephone and telecommunication, banking, postal and courier services, employment agencies, computer programming, information relating to higher and professional education, career counselors, advertising and marketing, research, consultancy, accountancy, hotels, restaurants, wholesaling, telecasting, share and stock broking, healthcare and health clubs, beauty parlors, beauticians, tourism, business process outsourcing etc. in rural India. This creates a big social gap between the urban and the rural.

In view of the existing dichotomy in availability of the services in urban and rural areas creating a yawning gap between rural and urban masses of the society, a strategic model - "Rural Business Strategic Model" has been developed for marketing the various urban facilities in the rural areas of Uttar Pradesh. The model elucidates the strategies for marketing of especially courier services, beauty parlors and computer education, which are easily available to, and accessible by urban people and not by rural and suburban people, in the rural and suburban areas of Uttar Pradesh.

Key Words: Services, Strategy, Rural Marketing and Business Model

Introduction

India is an agrarian economy and agriculture continues to be the mainstay of the Indian economy. Agriculture remains a significant contributor, as its contribution to the national Gross Domestic Product is about 18 per cent followed by manufacturing sector 26.4% of GDP. Around, 58.6 per cent of the Indian population earns its livelihood from agricultural and agricultural-related allied activities (such as cooperatives, fishing, dairies, etc.) compared to less than 10 per cent dependent on organized services sector, but does not have access to urban facilities.

Statistics reveal that in developed countries, services account for 75% of jobs and contribute nearly 70% of GNP. In developing and less developed countries, the share of services in GNP is generally lower compared to developed countries, but it is growing at a faster speed in the countries like India. ¹The service sector, which was contributing 26.3% of GDP in 1960-61, contributed 34.5% in 1970-71, 49% in 2001-02, 51.0% in 2002-03, 54.8% in 2007-08, 57% in 2010-11 and 59% in 2011-12.

Some of the examples of growing urban facilities in the state are: courier services, beauty parlors, and computer education considered specifically for study purposes and advertising and marketing, research, consultancy,

¹ Economic Survey 2011-12

accountancy, medicine, education, healthcare and health clubs, and hotel, restaurants, tourism, retailing, e-commerce, transport, telephone and telecommunication, broadcasting and telecasting, banking, share and stock broking, postal and employment agencies, computer software services and business process outsourcing in general. Information technology has made the world boundary less, thus widens the scope for services.

But these services have remained as urban facilities not available to rural areas of the country. To bridge the gap between urban and rural living standard, the former President, Dr. A P J Abdul Kalam, has been advocating the concept of PURA (Providing Urban amenities in Rural Areas), which he has made the core of his Vision 2020, with missionary zeal. After a long journey of 60 years of so called sustainable development after independence, the urban facilities could not reach out to rural areas. Prime Minister Dr. Man Mohan Singh recently talked about his vision for rural India: "My vision of rural India is of a modern agrarian, industrial and services economy co-existing side by side, where people can live in well-equipped villages and commute easily to work, be it on the farm or in the non-farm economy. There is much that modern science and technology can do to realize this vision. Rural incomes have to be increased. Rural infrastructure has to be improved. Rural health and education needs have to be met. Employment opportunities have to be created in rural areas."

However, the different developmental schemes of the government like Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Employment Guarantee Scheme, and National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) etc. for the rural people have changed the market scenario. Rural youth is now more aware and well informed of the services due to media. Lifestyle, habits and tastes, economic status have improved. Literacy level is more than 69.72% in 2011. People in rural areas want to have access to the urban amenities even with their low rate of increasing income.

The features of the existing rural markets are large and scattered, low standard of living, traditional outlook, diverse socio-economic backwardness and poor infrastructure facilities. The major problems faced in the rural areas of the state are underdeveloped people and under developed markets, ethnic problems facing people, many dialects, dispersed markets, low per capita income, low levels of literacy, prevalence of spurious brands and seasonal demand and a different way of thinking.

Rural markets face the critical issues of Distribution, Understanding the rural consumer, Communication and Poor infrastructure. The marketer has to strengthen the distribution and pricing strategies. The rural consumer expects value for money and owing to has unsteady and meager status of weekly income; increasing the household income and improving distribution are the viable strategies that have to be adapted to tap the immense potential of the market.

However, no organized efforts have been made by the other services' companies in the direction of strategy formulation for marketing of services in rural India like: medical facilities, vaccination, fast foods, matrimonial services, retailing, e-commerce, telephone and telecommunication, banking, postal and courier services, employment agencies, computer programming, information relating to higher and professional education, career counselors, advertising and marketing, research, consultancy, accountancy, hotels, restaurants, wholesaling, telecasting, share and stock broking, healthcare and health clubs, beauty parlors, beauticians, tourism, business process outsourcing. This creates a big social gap between the urban and the rural.

In rural markets, services primarily comprise retail trading, transportation and communication, financial services, healthcare, housing and construction, education, beauty parlor services, computer education, and community and social services. The services rendered in rural areas are not at par with its urban counter part in terms of quality, competitive price and professionalism.

In view of the existing dichotomy in availability of the services in urban and rural areas creating a yawning gap between rural and urban masses of the society, a strategic model - "Rural Business Strategic Model" has been developed for marketing the various urban facilities in the rural areas of Uttar Pradesh. The model elucidates the strategies for marketing of especially courier services, beauty parlors and computer education, which are easily available to, and accessible by urban people and not by rural and suburban people, in the rural and suburban

areas of Uttar Pradesh. The model is based on the outcomes of the research work of my Ph. D. Thesis titled “Strategy for marketing of services in rural Uttar Pradesh”.

The Rural Business Strategic Model

The model calls for developing strategies for marketing of especially courier services, beauty parlors and computer education, which are easily available to, and accessible by urban people and not by rural and suburban people, in the rural and suburban areas of Uttar Pradesh.

The steps involved in the strategic model (Fig. -1)for services in rural markets are: 1- Determining business mission or objective, 2- SWOT analysis, 3- Analyzing rural marketing mix challenges, 4-Designing appropriate services marketing mix for rural markets, 5-Developing service blue print with mass customization approach, 6- delivering final services to the rural customers, 7- evaluating and controlling the service performance.

Fig.-1 RBS Model

1-Determining business mission or objective

The mission is a value statement around which the entire corporate strategy revolves. A mission statement defines the scope of the business and long term vision of an organization. A mission statement -

- should define what the organization is and what the organization aspires to be
- should be limited enough to exclude some ventures and broad enough to allow for creative growth
- should distinguish a given organization from all others
- should serve as a framework for evaluating both current and prospective activities
- should be stated in terms sufficiently clear to the widely understood through out the future.

2- SWOT Analysis

A critical review of the strengths of the organization helps to identify its core competencies and define them in proper perspective. Strengths are internal competencies which may encompass company image, brand image, financial, personnel, marketing, production and research and development resources.

Every firm should develop a list of its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats periodically and evaluate all of them in the light of the company’s mission. The business unit should have an overall evaluation of

opportunities and the threats in the external environment and strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment so as to assess the core competencies and their adoptability to the changes in the external environment.

3- Analyzing rural marketing mix challenges

The rural market may be large and alluring but it is not without its problems: low per capita disposable incomes that is half the urban disposable income; large number of daily wage earners, acute dependence on the vagaries of the monsoon; seasonal consumption linked to harvests and festivals and special occasions; poor roads; power problems; and inaccessibility to conventional advertising media.

The companies are meeting the consequent challenges of availability, affordability, acceptability and awareness (the so-called 4 As).

The first challenge is to ensure availability of the product or service. India's 627,000 villages are spread over 3.2 million sq km; 700 million Indians may live in rural areas, finding them is not easy. The second challenge is to ensure affordability of the product or service. With low disposable incomes, products need to be affordable to the rural consumer, most of who are on daily wages. Some companies have addressed the affordability problem by introducing small unit packs. The third challenge is to gain acceptability for the product or service. Therefore, there is a need to offer products that suit the rural market. Mass media is able to reach only to 57% of the rural population. Creating awareness then, means utilizing targeted, unconventional media including ambient media. For generating awareness, events like fairs and festivals, Haats, etc., are used as occasions for brand communication.

4- Designing appropriate services marketing mix for rural areas

The most appropriate services marketing mix for rural areas are product, price, place, promotion, process, people and physical evidence, the same as urban markets. The seven Ps for the products under consideration are explained in the following paragraph.

Product: The Products (courier services, beauty parlors and computer education) provided to rural customers may differ from that of urban customers as services under study are not fully diffused in the rural segment. Due to lack of awareness and unavailability of the services, the rural customers are not accustomed to these kinds of services, but, they do have strong desire for the same.

Price: The price of these services as expected by the rural customer should be lesser as compared to urban customer due to the fact that income level as well as savings pattern of the rural customer are lesser.

Place: The place of availability is of very intense concern in rural markets due to lack of adequate and proper transportation facilities in rural India. The rural customers face major problems with the availability of service location in vicinity and thus are reluctant to derive benefits due to lack of travel support. The use of social infrastructure may be of great relevance. Most small towns are close to villages, with each town catering to the requirements of as many as 200 adjoining villages. These towns act as hubs in the distribution channel, with villages as the spokes. These small towns have become the preferred destination for rural masses to buy products and access major services.

Promotions: The promotional strategies in rural marketing needs to be more personalized and simple as compared to the urban markets which needs to reach more remote areas. The promotional tools also need to be customized according to the regional languages so that it clearly states the service details and benefits. As regards communication infrastructure, rural India is now changing. There are almost 80 million television sets in rural India, which means every second house has one. They are now getting all the required exposure.

Physical evidence: The physical evidence provided to the rural segment differ from that of the urban markets as they need to be more simple, colorful, artistic and personalized and thus need to be clearly explained about the features and benefits of the services thus provided. By the very nature of services being intangible, customers cannot see the service provided to them, but they can definitely see the tangibles associated, examine them and try to form an opinion on the service provider. Hence, physical evidence plays a critical role in shaping consumer perceptions and also expectations.

People: The people and staff appointed for the service delivery for the services under consideration in rural markets need to be properly selected, recruited and trained to understand the rural customer's needs and requirements. They need to be made well aware of the regional, cultural, social, economic and technological needs of the customers.

7. Process: Process is a functional activity that assures service availability and quality. The way the physical setting is designed technically and how the functions are scheduled and routed to provide promised services to the customers speaks of the efficiency of the process.

5- Developing service blue print with mass customization approach

One of the distinctive characteristics of service is that the production and consumption of service should take place simultaneously. The production process is done at a point where the service provider encounters the service customer, which makes the services delivery highly customized. The most significant aspect in the service production is that the customers are the co-producers. Taking this into account the service blue print should be developed with a mass customization approach which aims at meeting the service needs of large number of customers satisfactorily producing sizeable profit.

However, customized service package is the most desirable package from the rural customers' point of view, as they always want to drive core benefits in the service encounters which suits their needs and wants. For this, the concept of mass customization approach should be adopted. Mass customization refers to an approach in which the service principle tries to meet the highly specific needs of the customers (market niche) at mass scale. The practice of this concept is profitable in rural markets which are large and where customers prefer to a low price packaged product.

6-Delivering final services to the rural customers

Whatever be the package the service firms choose to offer, they need to follow a process for the development of a new service. The steps involved in the process are idea generation, idea screening, concept development and testing, concept testing, marketing-strategy development, business analysis, market testing, commercialization

7- Evaluating and controlling the service performance

Strategy evaluation at various levels of its implementation is essential to identify the deviations, if any, at an appropriate time and to initiate corrective action. There may be many hurdles in the process of strategy implementation, internally and externally some new problems may arise due to the implementation of the strategy and some problems may immerge due to unexpected changes in the environment. Service firms have to exercise strategic surveillance for timely detection of such development and take necessary corrective action. For the purpose of evaluation and control, an effective system has to be designed as given below-

- 1- Establishment of evaluation criteria and standards
- 2- Measuring and comparing performance
- 3- Identification and analysis of performance gap
- 4- Initiating corrective measure

However, the GAP model of service quality which was developed by Parasuraman, Zeithamal and Berry serves to the purpose, if executed properly.

Strategic recommendations Courier Services, Beauty Parlors and Computer Education

To enter into the rural markets, companies and service outlets need to keep in mind the following Do's and Don'ts before making strategic decisions about the service quality:

Do's for delivering Courier Services, Beauty Parlors and Computer education in rural markets:

- The focus of the service quality should be customer driven and hence need to be customized as per the requirements of customers in rural areas wanting value for their money.
- The service providers should be clearly aware of the local languages, culture and behavior of the rural customers. Thus the inclusion of local employees would be beneficial for the service provider to deal effectively with the customers.
- The service outlets should be able to provide highly customized and individualized services as per the needs of the customers in the rural markets

The service providers need to clearly understand the best possible location for its setup and operations as the location and facility layout of the service provider plays a very significant role in rural markets for the services under question because the rural areas do not have sufficient transport facilities like urban markets.

Each town market should be treated as hubs in the distribution channel, with villages as the spokes, as most small towns are close to villages, with each town catering to the requirements of as many as 200 adjoining villages.

- The customers should be made aware clearly about the services provided by the service outlets through effective physical evidence and promotions that should be made as simple as possible to the rural customers to understand properly.

The assistance should be provided regularly to the customers to educate them about the current as well as prospective facilities and benefits derived from the services provided by the service outlets.

Quality service should be delivered and errors should be treated as opportunities to excel in the field. The service companies should focus on the transactions delighting the customers, capitalizing on the human element, developing standards for technical quality empowerment and recovery strategies for service quality, performance quality, customer retention and building lasting and creative customer relationships.

The service companies should gain larger economies of scale on speed, flexibility, and ability to respond, reliability for unique standards.

Finally, the service outlets should focus on total customer delivered value.

Don'ts for delivering Courier Services, Beauty Parlors and Computer education in rural markets:

- Do not put much focus on providing any complex and unessential services.
- Do not use any unethical means for delivering the services. Consumables, in case of beauty parlor services, should be of high quality not resulting any damage or hazardous to the customers.
- Do not provide services to the customer before properly educating them about service benefits, performance process and time and money required to deliver the service so as to avoid confusion and discrepancy.
- Do not focus on the short term profitability, as building long term relationship with the customer by increasing total delivered customer value.

Conclusion

Rural market requires products with decent performance at very low cost. It is advised that companies are to aim 75% performance and 25% cost. Nirma or Ghadi washing powders are excellent lower performance, low cost products compared to the global Surf or Ariel brands. Rural consumers want to drive core benefits from the products and these low- priced brands clean clothes adequately.

The biggest challenge in rural India remains reaching your product to 600000 villages compared to 5000 towns in the urban areas. A few new rural distribution and procurement models have been innovated by ITC e-choupal and HUL project, shakti. But much more needs to be done in this area. One possibility is the use of social infrastructure being created by the government

Companies need to shift power where growth is by dedicating empowered teams for the rural markets so that they can develop their own strategies and products. A separate sales force is also desirable as the regular force will avoid covering the more difficult and small off-take rural markets.

In view of the challenges, prospects, scope, demand conditions, purchasing capability, large and scattered market size of rural markets of the sample area under consideration, RBS Model (Rural Business Strategic Model) is, hereby, suggested for the companies planning to take up any new entrepreneurial venture in the field of the three service under consideration.

Moreover, the rural market of India is an untapped and vastly spread market having lot of potential and challenges too for any entrepreneurial venture in the field of services in the rural markets. The outcomes are highly stimulating for different interest groups to tap the untapped rural market. Also, there are lot possibilities for further research in the field. The academicians, researchers, professionals, companies and the government are highly encouraged to explore the possibilities for marketing of other important services in the widely spread market of rural India.

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4Ps Business & Marketing, Vol.-5, Issue – 3, February 2012